

Studies on Triligand Complexes of some Lanthanones

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The results of pH-metric studies on the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 MLL'L'' quaternary complexes, where $M = \text{La}^{\text{III}}, \text{Pr}^{\text{III}}, \text{Nd}^{\text{III}}$; $L = 1,2\text{-diaminocyclohexane-}N,N,N',N'\text{-tetraacetic acid (CDTA)}$; $L' = 1,2\text{-dihydroxysuccinic acid (tartaric acid)}$; and $L'' = 2\text{-butenedioic acid (maleic acid)}$, have been discussed in the present paper. The calculated values of formation constants and free energy of formation of the resulting quaternary species, formed by the simultaneous chelation of all the three ligands to the metal ion, have been compared with those of the 1 : 1 : 1 M-CDTA-TAR/MIA ternary complex at constant temperature (15°) and ionic strength (0.1 M KNO_3) of the medium. A comparison of the values of stability constants both in ternary as well as in quaternary complexes reveal the order, $\text{La}^{\text{III}} < \text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}}$ in terms of metal ions, ternary < quaternary in terms of complex species, and tartaric acid > maleic acid in the case of dicarboxylic acids. The calculated values of the percentage dissociation (0.2746) of the ligand, in the case of quaternary complex formation indicate that maleic acid behaves as monodentate ligand in the lower pH range.

DURING the last decade, a considerable work has been reported on the formation of ternary complexes of rare earths¹⁻³ but comparatively less work has been reported on the quaternary complexes of lanthanones⁴⁻⁷, probably due to their high electro-positive and hydrolytic nature. However, a survey of the literature reveals that rare earth ions expand their coordination number in mixed ligand complex formation. This idea led us to investigate some more 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 quaternary systems of lanthanones potentiometrically with a view to ascertain their formation, and to see the effect on the coordination number of the metal ion by the addition of one more ligand in ternary complex forming quaternary species.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of either AnalaR (B.D.H.) or G.R. (E. Merck) grades. All the solutions were prepared in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. Standard solutions of lanthanide nitrates were prepared and standardised by the reported methods^{8,9}. The solutions of tartaric acid, maleic acid, potassium nitrate and potassium hydrogenphthalate were prepared by direct weighing. CDTA was used in its mono-protonated form. The concentrations of the ligand and metal nitrate solutions were further checked potentiometrically.

pH measurements were carried out with Toshniwal CL 46 digital pH meter keeping ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$), total volume (50 ml) and temperature ($15 \pm 1^\circ$) constant as described earlier^{8,9}.

Formation constants: The dissociation constants of tripotassium-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetate ($K_3\text{CDTA}$) ($pK = 10.13 \pm 0.07$), tartaric acid (TAR) ($pK_1 = 2.91 \pm 0.10$, $pK_2 = 4.17 \pm 0.06$) and

maleic acid (MIA) ($pK_1 = 2.17 \pm 0.08$, $pK_2 = 6.04 \pm 0.05$) were evaluated by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹⁰. The formation constants ($\log K_{\text{MLL}'}$, $\log K_{\text{MLL}'L''}$) of ternary and quaternary complexes were calculated by the modified method⁴ of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹¹.

Deprotonation constants: In quaternary complexes, the second ionisation constant ($-\log K_A^{\text{H}}$) of the coordinated dicarboxylic acid (MIA) was calculated by the method of Dey and Nayan¹².

Results and Discussion

The pH-metric curves of all the three involved metal ions were found to be very similar in nature. Hence, the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 M-CDTA-TAR-MIA quaternary complex is shown by the curves of lanthanum (Fig. 1) for the sake of brevity. Curve (a) giving an inflection at $m \approx 2.6$ represents the basic-salt formation^{13,14} of metal. Curve (b) for tripotassium salt of CDTA is ascribed to the non-titrable nature of the remaining carboxylic protons¹⁵. Curve (c) showing a single well-defined inflection at $m = 2$, is attributed to the simultaneous titration of both the carboxylic protons of TAR, and curve (d) for MIA, exhibits two inflections at $m = 1$ and 2 due to the titration of two carboxylic protons at different pH values.

Binary systems: Curve (e) (Fig. 1) shows the M-CDTA binary complex formation¹⁶ and the occurrence of two inflections at $m = 2$ and 3.5 on the curve (f) may be attributed to 1 : 1 La^{III} -TAR at lower pH and 1 : 2 La^{III} -TAR¹⁶ complex in higher buffer region, respectively. Similarly, 1 : 1 La^{III} -MIA complex formation¹⁷ is represented by two inflections at $m = 2$ and 4, respectively as depicted by curve (g).

Fig. 1. System 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-OTDA-TAR-MIA : (a) La(NO₃)₃, (b) K₃CDTA, (c) TAR, (d) MIA, (e) La^{III}-OTDA, (f) La^{III}-TAR, (g) La^{III}-MIA, (h) La^{III}-OTDA-TAR, (i) La^{III}-OTDA-MIA, (j) La^{III}-OTDA-TAR-MIA, (T) theoretical composite curve and (↓) appearance of precipitate.

Ternary systems : The initial lowering in pH as compared to the curves (c) and (f) and an inflection at m=3 on the curve (h) (Fig. 1) illustrating the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-CDTA-TAR system, may be ascribed to the simultaneous chelation of both the ligands to the metal ion resulting in the formation of a soluble ternary species¹⁵. Curve (i) representing the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-CDTA-MIA ternary system, exhibits an appreciable lowering in pH due to complexation of metal ions. An inflection at m=2 may be ascribed to the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-CDTA-MIA monoprotonated soluble ternary species. The deprotonation of this protonated complex occurs in the higher buffer region as shown by the appearance of a solid phase throughout the titration and by the non-superimposable nature of

the curves (h) and (i) with the binary curves (e, f, and g) further substantiating the formation of hetero-ligand ternary species.

Quaternary systems : Curve (j) (Fig. 1) illustrates the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-CDTA-TAR-MIA system. An initial lowering in pH right from the beginning as compared to that exhibited by the curves representing binary and ternary systems and by an inflection at m=4 may be correlated with the titration of only four protons of the three ligands, one each from K₃CDTA and MIA and two from TAR, forming 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La^{III}-CDTA-TAR-MIA diprotonated quaternary species. This soluble complex appears to undergo deprotonation in the higher pH range giving a normal quaternary complex as shown by one more inflection at m=5. The absence of any solid phase during the titration, the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve T¹⁵ (drawn by adding the horizontal distance of curve (c) and (i) to the curve (j) in the region of mixed ligand complex formation), and the evaluated values of stability constants lend additional support to the proposed quaternary complex formation.

The ligand L''(MIA) behaves as monobasic acid in the pH range 2.39-3.81. The almost negligible values of percentage dissociation of the second proton of the acid (for MIA=0.2746 at pH=3.81) evaluated¹⁹, indicate that the second proton of MIA remains almost intact in the mentioned pH range.

Formation constants of mixed ligand species : The relative order of stability for ternary and quaternary species (log K_{MLL'}, log K_{MLL''} and log K_{MLL'L''}, respectively) in terms of metal ions has been found to be, La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III}, and may be explained

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANT AND FREE ENERGY OF FORMATION

Metal ions	1 : 1 : 1 M-CDTA-TAR/MIA				1 : 1 : 1 M-CDTA-TAR-MIA	
	TAR		MIA		log K _{MLL'L''}	°G kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	log K _{MLL'}	°G kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	log K _{MLL''}	°G kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹		
La ^{III}	8.38 ± 0.08	-11.04	4.43 ± 0.08	-5.84	16.85 ± 0.09	-22.21
Pr ^{III}	8.59 ± 0.10	-11.32	4.58 ± 0.12	-6.04	17.17 ± 0.16	-22.63
Nd ^{III}	8.72 ± 0.06	-11.94	4.73 ± 0.13	-6.23	17.52 ± 0.14	-13.09

on the basis of decreasing size and increasing charge/radius ratio of the metal ions. In terms of ternary and quaternary complexes, the observed trend, quaternary > ternary, may be due to the increased number of fused chelate rings²⁰ in quaternary complexes. In the case of 1:1:1 M-CDTA-TAR/MIA, the greater stability of the tartaric acid complexes in comparison to that of the maleic acid complexes, is probably due to the increased number of coordination centres and its basicity.

Deprotonation constant: Calculated values of the second ionisation constant (deprotonation constant, $-\log K_A^H$) of the protonated quaternary species are given in the Table 2. The lower calculated values of $-\log K_A^H$ in comparison to the pK_a values of MIA are of significance and may be attributed to the liberation of the second carboxylic proton of the acid coordinated to the metal ion in quaternary complexes.

TABLE 2—DEPROTONATION CONSTANT

Metal ions	1 : 1 : 1 M-ODTA-TAR-MIA
La ^{III}	5.94 ± 0.04
Pr ^{III}	5.90 ± 0.04
Nd ^{III}	5.86 ± 0.04

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